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CULTURE, COMMUNICATION AND LANGUAGE: TRIPOD OF HUMAN EXISTENCE

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Abstract

Each individual is unique in nature, selective in preferences, collective in approach, cumulative in judgement and cultured in behaviour. No two individuals in this world are similar to each other and everyone maintains a kind of variation. Such variations can be termed as individual uniqueness. In spite of these individual uniqueness and variations, we as a human being prefer to live in a group, use common codes of communication. Both language and society are autonomous but interdependent and inseparable. In its neutral form, a language is mere a game of signs and sounds; and communication is the process of conveying information; and culture is a storehouse of values and norms. Language is a cultural creation and culture is embedded in use of a language; and the meaning is constructed, constituted, and conveyed within the cultural domain.

Culture, communication, and language can be considered as a tripod of human existence. This paper makes an effort to develop an understanding about their interrelatedness and influence on human life and actions.

Keywords: culture, communication, language, etc.